

SYNTHESIS OF α -ALKYL- γ -(2-METHOXY-5-CHLOROPHENYL)- BUTYRO LACTONES

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α -Alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids, prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction between *p*-chloroanisole and alkylsuccinic anhydrides, have been reduced and lactonised to furnish the corresponding α -alkyl- γ -(2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

In continuation with the work described in previous paper (*this issue*, p. 521) α -alkyl- γ -(2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones have been synthesised.

p-Chloroanisole was condensed with alkylsuccinic anhydrides in the presence of aluminium chloride in acetylene tetrachloride and nitrobenzene solvent to obtain α -alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids. Except in the case of methylsuccinic anhydride, with other anhydrides the products obtained were partially demethylated. Such demethylation has been observed in the succinylation of pyrogallol trimethyl ether when β -(2-hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid instead of (2:3:4-trimethoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid was obtained (Bargellini and Gina, *Gazzetta*, 1912, 42, 197; Manske and Holmes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1945, 67, 95; Dalal, Bokil and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1939, 8, Part II, 203; Mitter and De, *this Journal*, 1939, 16, 35). Therefore these α -alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were prepared by any of the following methods:

(a). Pure α -alkyl- β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were obtained by the condensation of *p*-chlorophenol with alkylsuccinic anhydrides in acetylene tetrachloride solvent and these were methylated by dimethyl sulphate in alkali solution. α -Ethyl-, α -*n*-propyl- and α -*n*-butyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were prepared by this method.

(b). The mixed acids obtained in the condensation of *p*-chloroanisole with alkylsuccinic anhydride were esterified and the mixed esters were methylated by dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone solution. The product on hydrolysis gave α -alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid. α -*n*-Hexyl acid was prepared by this method.

By analogy with the work described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*), the structures of the keto-acids have been assumed to be α -alkyl type.

On oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate, the keto-acids gave an acid (m.p. 81°-82°) which was identical with (mixed m.p.) methyl ether of 5-chlorosalicylic acid (Peratoner and Condorelli, *Gazzetta*, 1898, 28, 211). Thus, these keto-acids are α -alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The condensation of *p*-chloroanisole with alkylsuccinic anhydride was carried out as described in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of p-Chlorophenol with Alkylsuccinic Anhydride.—*p*-Chlorophenol (12.6 g., 0.1 *M*), alkylsuccinic anhydride (0.1 *M*) and tetrachloroethane (75 c.c.) were taken in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a condenser carrying a calcium chloride guard tube. To the cooled reaction mixture aluminium chloride (27 g., 0.2 *M*) was added in small lots with stirring. The mixture was heated in an oil-bath for about 3 hours at 120°. It was cooled and decomposed with ice and HCl and α -alkyl- β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was isolated as usual. The methylation of α -alkyl- β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was done by dimethyl sulphate as described by Trivedi and Nargund (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1942, 11, Part III, 127).

α -n-Hexyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic Acid.—The mixed keto-acids, obtained in the condensation of *n*-hexylsuccinic anhydride (18.4 g., 0.1 *M*) with *p*-chloroanisole (12.6 g., 0.1 *M*), were esterified as usual. The mixed ester (9.0 g.), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (9 g.) dry acetone (40 c.c.) and dimethyl sulphate (4.0 g.) were refluxed on a water-bath for 12 hours. Acetone was removed and the residue was hydrolysed with alcoholic KOH solution (10%, 30 c.c.) by boiling for 4 hours. Alcohol was distilled off on a water-bath and the residue was diluted with water and acidified when α -*n*-hexyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid separated.

The reduction of α -alkyl- β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was effected as described previously (*loc. cit.*). Yield of the lactone was 40 to 55%. The compounds are tabulated in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

PA denotes β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid.

P'A ,, β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid.

No.	Name of the compound.	Formula.	Properties.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	α -Methyl- β -PA	$C_{12}H_{13}O_4Cl$	Needles from hot water, m.p. 120°.	14.0 (255.0)	13.8 (256.5)
2.	Ethyl ester of (1)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. 2:3-18°/10 mm. "n ²⁰ , 1.536.	12.8	12.4
3.	2:4-D.N.P. of (1)	$C_{18}H_{17}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 178°.	8.3	8.1
4.	α -Ethyl- β -PA	$C_{12}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Small needles from dil. alcohol, m.p. 147°.	14.1	13.8
5.	α -Ethyl-PA	$C_{13}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Needles from hot water, m.p. 105°.	13.3 (272.5)	13.1% (270.5)
6.	Ethyl ester of (5)	$C_{15}H_{19}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. 217-22/10 mm. "n ²⁰ , 1.529.	12.1	11.9
7.	2:4-D.N.P. of (5)	$C_{19}H_{19}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 190°.	8.1	7.9
8.	α - <i>n</i> -Propyl-P'A	$C_{13}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Needles from hot water, m.p. 118°.	13.0	13.1
9.	α - <i>n</i> -Propyl-PA	$C_{14}H_{17}O_4Cl$	White granules from petroleum ether, m.p. 92°.	12.6 (286.0)	12.5 (284.5)
10.	Ethyl ester of (9)	$C_{16}H_{21}O_4Cl$	Liquid, b.p. 187-92°/1 mm. "n ²⁰ , 1.516.	11.6	11.4
11.	2:4-D.N.P. of (9)	$C_{20}H_{21}O_7N_4Cl$	Yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 183°.	7.8	7.6

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Name of the compound.	Formula.	Properties.	Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.
12.	<i>n</i> -Butyl-P'A	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	Needles from hot water, m.p. 168°.	12.7	12.5
13.	<i>n</i> -Butyl-PA	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	White granules from pet. ether, m.p. 95°	12.1 (297.0)	11.9 (298.5)
14.	Ethyl ester of (13)	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	Liquid, b.p. 195-200°/3.5 mm. n _D ²⁰ , 1.516.	20.9	20.9
15.	2:4-D.N.P. of (13)	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₄ Cl	Yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 205°.	7.7	7.4
16.	<i>n</i> -Hexyl-PA	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ Cl	Needles from benzene-petrol, m.p. 114°.	11.0 (328.1)	10.9 (326.5)
17.	Ethyl ester of (16)	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ O ₄ Cl	Liquid, b.p. 140-45°/7 mm. n _D ²⁰ , 1.468.	10.3	10.0
18.	2:4 D.N.P. of (16)	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ O ₇ N ₄ Cl	Yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 192°.	6.8	7.0

N.D. D.N.P denotes dinitrophenylhydrazone.
 Figures in parentheses in last two columns refer to equiv. wt.

TABLE II

No.	Alkyl γ -(2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.	Formula.	Properties.	% Chlorine.		Eq. weights.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>n</i> -Methyl.	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl	Liquid, b.p. 202-207°/6 mm. n _D ²⁰ , 1.556	14.8	14.8	238.2	240.5
2.	<i>n</i> -Ethyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₃ Cl	Liquid, b.p. 227-32°/9 mm. n _D ²⁶ , 1.545	14.2	14.0	255.7	254.5
3.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ Cl	Liquid, b.p. 210-15°/2 mm. n _D ²⁶ , 1.548	13.5	13.2	266.3	268.5
4.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₃ Cl	Liquid b.p. 175-80°/3.5 mm. n _D ²⁶ , 1.547	12.6	12.6	280.6	282.2
5.	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ Cl	Plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 85°.	11.5	11.4	312.1	310.5

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